

Workplace Learning Effectiveness and Internal Service Quality in the Public Sector: Development of an Instrument and Testing of a Predictive Structural Model

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Abstract. The purpose of this study is to develop an instrument of measure for the influence of Human Resource Development on internal service quality in the Public Sector in Mauritius. The study will firstly identify the workplace learning methods which employees perceive as effective for service quality delivery and then identify the perceived influencing factors affecting the achievement of service quality delivery when an employee learns in the workplace. This will be followed by the investigation of the relationship between the influencing factors of workplace learning and service quality delivery and the perceived effectiveness of workplace learning.

The study will be guided by the research question: What are the perceived influencing factors affecting the achievement of service quality delivery when employees learn in the workplace? It is proposed to use the 3 P's model (Presage, Process and Product) by Tynjala, (2013), derived from Biggs (1987) and modified accordingly to suit workplace learning, to answer the research questions. Presage includes learner factors or individual factors and learning context or organizational factors and the product relates to the outcomes of learning, while the process is the means through which employees learn (formal and/or informal methods).

Workplace learning englobes a wide variety of learning activities under formal and informal learning and has common elements: gain in knowledge, skills and attitude. The way individual learn in organisations are influenced by both individual and organizational factors. At individual level: motivation, job satisfaction, reflection, self-efficacy, self-confidence, demographics (age), and at organisational level: team work, work environment, leadership, supervisor support, access to information, communication amongst others will be investigated in relation to the research question.

Internal service quality of employees in the public sector is crucial for the delivery of service quality to external customers. Can this be done without a well-developed human resource? What is the role of learning and development in the achievement of this objective? The research aims to benefit scholars by bringing additional knowledge to the literature, and equip practitioners with appropriate tool to respond to the challenges of the public sector in Mauritius.

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This study will introduce a unique model explaining the relationship between influencing factors and its efficiency and the mediating role of workplace learning to achieve internal service quality. Further this study will be among the few to use multilevel regression analysis for influencing factors of workplace learning at individual and organisational level to cover a sample of 400 employees from 24 Ministries in Mauritius. The development of the model and the testing of the hypothesis will make use of Structural Equation Modeling and ultimately to help bridge the gap between the two fields of study that is Human Resource Development and Internal Service Quality.

1 Background of Research

The main aim of Human Resource Development (HRD) through workplace learning is to maintain the human capital of the organisation up to date and ready to face present and future challenges (TKachenko, Seo & Ardichvili, 2022; Kim, Kwon & Choi, 2024; To and Leung, 2024). HRD is impacted by personal and organisational factors and a good learning climate and a proper mix of formal and informal learning will result in a highly knowledgeable and skilful workforce (Tynjala, 2013; Salcedo, Williams, Elias, Valencia & Perz, 2022). HRD cannot be limited to formal training and development activities to tackle all issues in the organisation, specifically the complex issues in the public sector. With a quality perspective in service delivery, the public sector through their respective administrators should have a different vision regarding the learning taking place in their respective ministries and agencies (Kleefstra, Altan, and Stoffers, 2020). This research focuses on an HRD measure and will study the influence of workplace learning on internal service quality delivery in the public sector in Mauritius.

2 Specific Problem being examined

There is a significant gap that needs consideration as this current study has not yet been established empirically in the literature and in so doing will extend the literature by adding evidence empirically that workplace learning has an impact on internal service quality improvement in the public sector. Further, some evidence suggests that the public sector has specific contextual characteristics that may set it apart from other industries in terms of organisational dynamics. As such, this research will organise all instruments of measures in organisations and will develop and validate a measure for workplace learning for internal service quality in the Public Sector.

The study aims to develop an instrument and testing of a Predictive Structural Model for Human Resource Development, Workplace Learning Effectiveness and Internal Service Quality in the Public Sector. The research questions express the purpose of the study so as to address the research problem. The research is based on the following questions while evaluating the factors influencing the development of an instrument of measure for Human Resource Development for Internal Service Quality delivery.

3 Methodological Approach

The overall objective of the research methodology adopted will be to collect data to help generate a good insight into the phenomenon of workplace learning in the public sector. The population of the public sector is about 75,000 (Statistics Mauritius, 2023) and these include Ministries and Parastatals. In order to focus on main service delivery, only ministries and their respective departments will be taken into consideration and the population is about 50,000 (Statistics Mauritius, 2023) government officers. The expected sample will be about 400 and will be from about 24 Ministries of the Government of Mauritius. Secondary data collection will be done through the literature search of books, journal articles, and online sources amongst others. The research papers and other relevant literature will be scrutinised to inform the researcher on the way an individual learns in organisations, what learning activities the individuals are engaged in and what are the potential influencing factors which affect the choice of these learning activities (Aggarwal, Dhaliwal and Nobi, 2018; Decius, 2019; 2021; 2023; Grosemans, et al., 2020) which will help to set the research questions and ultimately the research hypotheses. The collection of primary data will be done using a mixed-method approach (Rahman and Shiddike, 2020; Molina-Azorin, 2016; Antwi and Hamza, 2015; Molina-Azorin and Fetters, 2019; 2020). An interview will be conducted to gather additional information from managers (Lecat, Raemdonck, Beusaert, and Marz, 2019), and this will be followed by the administration of a questionnaire to sampled employees, online and by hand.

The second phase of this research will be to empirically test the conceptual framework. This will be done by using a quantitative approach to measure the objectives set and to answer the research questions. The quantitative approach will be used together with the qualitative approach for research questions 1 to 5. A mixed method approach will be used for this research, with a qualitative method based on the phenomenological approach together with a quantitative approach based on a post-positivist approach. Interviews will be held with Permanent Secretaries and Head of Departments and questionnaires will be administered to employees. The mixed method approach which makes use of qualitative and quantitative approaches is a possibility to give a better insight into the problem and thereafter the solution of the research questions to the researcher.

A triangulation (Decrop, 1999; Sim and Sharp, 1998; Donato et al., 2017) of the results obtained from each approach will be done to ascertain the data collected. Following a multilevel regression analysis for testing the factors at both the individual and organisational levels, a structural equation modelling will be used to test the hypothesis. There are several methods and methodologies that have been used to research workplace learning (Flemming and Zegwaard, 2018), both quantitative and qualitative.

4 Description of the Artifacts

Workplace learning involves a wide variety of learning activities under formal and informal learning and has common elements such as gain in knowledge, skills, and

attitude. The way individuals learn in organisations is influenced by both individual and organisational factors at the individual level and organisational level and will be investigated in relation to the research questions. The research aims to benefit scholars by bringing additional knowledge to the literature and equipping practitioners with appropriate tools to respond to the challenges of the public sector in Mauritius. This study will introduce a unique model explaining the relationship between influencing factors and the mediating role of workplace learning to achieve internal service quality. Further, this study will be among the few to use multilevel regression analysis for influencing factors of workplace learning at the individual and organisational level to cover a sample of 400 employees from 24 Ministries in Mauritius.

The author presents a synthesis of the current literature on workplace learning guided by the main research question: What are the factors which influence employees learning in the workplace? The psychological theories and the socio-cultural theories inform the development of the theoretical model of the study. It is proposed to use the 3 P's (Presage, Process, Product) model and modified accordingly to suit workplace learning. Presage includes learner factors or individual factors and learning context or organisational factors and the product relates to the outcomes of learning, while the process consists of the means through which employees learn; either through formal or informal learning or through a combination of both. Workplace learning involves a wide variety of learning activities under formal and informal learning and has common elements such as gain in knowledge, skills, and attitude. The way individuals learn in organisations is influenced by both personal and organisational factors. It is worth noting that many studies have focused on either personal factors or organisational factors, as influencing factors for the adoption of workplace learning, but very few have considered both types of factors in one study. The study reveals that personal factors such as reflection, task uncertainty, motivation, promotion opportunities, organisational commitment, job satisfaction, self-efficacy, and proactivity while organisational factors such as job characteristics, organisational and top management support, learning climate, and leadership are among the most influential factors which trigger the effectiveness of workplace learning in an organisation. Based on the above, the authors will evaluate the potential predictors and will propose a conceptual model for understanding workplace learning adoption using personal and organisational factors.

5 Expected Contribution of the Work

The literature suggests that there is some link between workplace learning and internal service quality (Tynjala, 2008; 2013). The aim is to develop a model and to identify the possible relationships between workplace learning and internal service quality. This study will introduce a unique model explaining the relationship between the influencing factors of workplace learning and its efficiency and its mediating role on internal service quality (Uhunoma, et al., 2021). The current study will be one of the few studies that will empirically relate learning factors, learning efficiency, and the outcomes of internal service quality while employees are in the process of learning in the workplace. It will offer a classification of the factors that lead to workplace learning efficiency and

internal service quality (Otoo et al., 2018). This research will attempt to pave the way for the development of a measure for HRD for internal service quality in the public sector and, as such will add to the existing literature by emphasizing the combination of formal and informal workplace learning in a distinctive context such as the public sector in which learning takes place (Kusaila, 2019). The use of structural equation modelling to bridge the gap between the two fields of research: Human Resource Development and Internal Service Quality.

6 Plan to assure Research Transparency

In this particular research like most research, the data collection will be primarily from human participants. We need to ensure that all approval is obtained from an ethical point of view before conducting the survey and distribution of questionnaires (Fleming, 2018), which includes the willingness of the individual to participate in the survey. Relevant permission will be sought from public bodies as and when required.

7 Summary

This research has main objective to develop an instrument of measure for HRD for internal service quality in public sector organisations. The study will allow the author and other researchers to have a better understanding of:

- i. the personal and organisational factors which influence the adoption of workplace learning;
- ii. the learning activities preferred by individuals in the workplace,
- iii. the relationship between workplace learning and internal service quality.

Further, the study will add to existing literature by considering both formal and informal workplace learning in one study; and will make use of structural equation modelling to test the hypothesis.

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